

BRIEF COMMUNICATION ON THE OPEN ACCESS NEEDS OF UKRAINIAN RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS AND UNIVERSITIES

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1. General summary

Between 13 and 20 April 2022, #ScienceForUkraine and the Young Scientist Council of the Ministry of Education gathered information on open access needs of Ukrainian universities and research institutes at the National Academy of Science (NAS) of Ukraine. In the survey, they were asked to identify specific publishing houses, journal families or individual journals, corresponding to universities'/institutes' primarily academic needs. As a result, the survey focused on:

- (i) publishing house and journal (PH&J) that should be easily accessed to facilitate normal scientific activities of the university/institute (e.g., open access is required for teaching, research, grant writing)
- (ii) PH&J that universities and research institute are regularly publishing in (e.g., publishing fee should be waived or reduced)

No distinction was made between the two aforementioned needs (i, ii), both of them are equally weighted in this document.

A total of 49 independent responses were received, on behalf of the entire university (2%, 1 case), the entire faculty, research department (24.5%, 12 cases) or as an individual (92.3%, 36 cases). Only university or departmental level submissions were considered in this report. The data is summarized according to six research areas, defined by the Frascati Manual (summarized in diagram 1).

1. The fields of science and technology classification

49 responses

Diagram 1. response distribution by research field.

Below one can find a list of universities and research institutes that participated in the survey:

- Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv (KNU)
- Astronomical Observatory of Ukraine
- Institute of Geology
- Institute of electrodynamics, power system automation
- V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Department of Plant and Microorganisms Physiology and Biochemistry
- V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Department of Zoology and Animal Ecology
- Chernihiv Polytechnic National University, Department of agricultural technologies and Forestry
- Institute of Magnetism, Department of Physics of Mezo- and Nanocrystalline Structures
- Institute of Journalism
- KNU, Department of probability theory, statistics and actuarial mathematics
- KNU, Operations Research Department
- KNU, the Educational and Scientific Institute of Public Administration and Civil Service

Of the response on behalf of the entire faculty or research department, 92.3% (11 cases) indicated that there is an imminent need for 500-1000 subscriptions per faculty or department. Only one of the 12 respondents (7.7%) indicated that 1000-5000 subscriptions were needed per faculty or department.

No (expected) publication frequency of scientific articles was indicated for exemptions from journal publication costs.

2. List of Prioritized Publishing houses

The following publishing houses were identified as the ones mainly needed for academic needs (i, ii) of Ukrainian universities and research institutes at the NAS of Ukraine (alphabetical order):

American Institute of Physics, American Physics Society, Cambridge University, EDP Sciences, IEEE, Elsevier, Institute of physics (England), IOP publishing, Oxford Academic, Physical Review D, Press, Routledge (Taylor & Francis Group), Sage, Springer, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, Bernoulli, Wiley.

3. List of Prioritized Journals by field

In addition, the following individual scientific journals were identified as the ones primarily needed for academic need (i, ii) of Ukrainian universities and research institutes at the NAS of Ukraine (per research focus).

3.1. AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

3.1.1. Titles of journals

- Journal of Cleaner Production - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-cleaner-production>

3.1.2. Universities who are interested in open access:

- Chernihiv Polytechnic National University / Department of agricultural technologies and Forestry

3.2. ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

3.2.1. Titles of journals

- Advances in Climate Change Research - <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/advances-in-climate-change-research>
- Applied Nanoscience (Switzerland) - <https://www.springer.com/journal/13204>
- International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems
- Journal of Physical Chemistry C - <https://pubs.acs.org/journal/jpcck>
- Physica E: Low-dimensional systems and nanostructures - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/physica-e-low-dimensional-systems-and-nanostructures>
- Plasmonics - <https://www.springer.com/journal/11468>
- Transactions on power systems

3.2.2. Universities who are interested in open access:

- Institute of electrodynamics National academy of Science, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, National university of food technologies

3.3. HUMANITIES

3.3.1. Titles of journals

- Journal of risk and insurance

3.3.2. Universities who are interested in open access

- Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv,
- Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman

3.4. MEDICAL AND HEALTH SCIENCES

3.4.1. Titles of journals

- Angewandte Chemie International Edition - <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/15213773>

3.4.2. Universities who are interested in open access:

- Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Odessa National Medical University

3.5. NATURAL SCIENCES

3.5.1. Titles of journals

- American Chemical Society (ACS) Publishing journals
- Astronomy and Astrophysics
- Applied Physics Letters - <https://aip.scitation.org/journal/apl>
- Advances in Applied Probability - <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/advances-in-applied-probability>
- Annals of Probability
- Annals of Statistics
- Clinical and Experimental Pharmacology and Physiology
- Electrochimica acta - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/electrochimica-acta>
- European Journal of Physics
- Frontiers in Pharmacology
- Geochemistry
- Journal of Geophysical Research. Atmosphere - <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/21698996>
- Icarus - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/icarus>
- Journal of Molecular liquids - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-molecular-liquids>
- Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter - <https://iopscience.iop.org/journal/0953-8984>
- Journal of Theoretical Probability
- Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics
- Journal of Geophysical Research. Planets - <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/21699100?tabActivePane=undefined>
- Journal of Applied Probability - <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-applied-probability>
- Journal of Environmental radioactivity - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-environmental-radioactivity>
- Journal of Nuclear Physics and Atomic Energy
- J. Exp. Bot., BIOL BIOCHEM, Functional Ecology, ACS Chemical Biology, Plant J., BMC Microbiology - <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/21698996>
- Journal of Physiology
- Journal of Physics
- Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society
- Molecular Ecology - <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1365294x>
- Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/molecular-phylogenetics-and-evolution>
- Nature, Nature Materials, Nature Physics, Nature Nanotechnology
- Nuclear Physics
- Physical Review Applied/B/E/Letters - <https://www.aps.org/publications/journals/index.cfm>
- Physical Review
- Physics Letters
- Physical Review D
- Physical Review Letters
- Physics Letters
- Probability Theory and Related Fields - <https://www.springer.com/journal/440>
- Problems of Atomic Science and Technology
- Statistical Inference for Sochastic Processes
- Science- <https://www.science.org/>
- Science, hydrobiological journal

Sensors and actuators B Chemistry - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/sensors-and-actuators-b-chemical>

- Stochastic Processes and Applications
- Stochastics, Statistics and Probability Letters

3.5.2. Universities who are interested in open access:

- Institute of Magnetism National academy of science
- V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University
- Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv

3.6. SOCIAL SCIENCES

3.6.1. Titles of journals

- American Economic Journal: Microeconomics - <https://www.aeaweb.org/journals/mic>
- AOM journals - <https://journals.aom.org/>
- Communication Research - <https://journals.sagepub.com/home/crx>
- Economic Policy - <https://academic.oup.com/economicpolicy>
- European Journal of the History of Economic Thought - <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/rejh20>
- Investment Analysts Journal
- International marketing research - www.journals.sagepub.com
- International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business
- International Journal of Industrial Organization - <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/international-journal-of-industrial-organization>
- Journal of financial economics, The review of financial studies, Journal of corporate finance
- Journal of Business Research - <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-business-research>
- Journal of Business and Economic Statistics - <https://amstat.tandfonline.com/loi/ubes>
- Journal of Corporate Real Estate
- Review of Corporate Finance Studies
- Journal of Corporate Finance
- Journal of Financial Intermediation
- Journal of Investing
- Journal of Investment Strategies
- Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment
- Journal of Property Investment and Finance
- Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory
- Journalism Practice - <https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/rjop20/current>
- Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly - <https://journals.sagepub.com/home/jmq>
- Journal of Political Economy Microeconomics - <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/journals/jpe/micro>
- Strategic Management Journal - <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10970266>

3.6.2. Universities who are interested in open access:

- Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman
- Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv

Google Sheet with answers is available here:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/16hjN_B_cmohxAUdJtfcJSSk_EcQOvwZrnTs739T6_I/edit?resourcekey#gid=2002403283